

Journal of Politics and Development

ISSN 2632-4911

Volume 15 ■ Number 2 ■ Summer 2025

the rest: journal of politics and development

Previously published as Journal of Global Analysis (JGA)

Editors-in-Chief:

Ozgur TUFEKCI, Assoc. Prof. | Karadeniz Technical University, Türkiye & CESRAN International
Rahman DAG, Assoc. Prof. | Marmara University, Türkiye & CESRAN International

Associate Editors:

Alessia CHIRIATTI, Dr. | Istituto Affari Internazionali, Italy
Marco MARSILI, Dr. | Ca' Foscari University, Italy & CESRAN International

Assistant Editors:

Ekrem OK | Agri Ibrahim Cecen University, Türkiye & CESRAN International
Rabia BUYUKPINAR | Zonguldak Bulent Ecevit University, Türkiye & CESRAN International

Editorial Board

Sener AKTURK, Prof. | Koç University, Turkey
Enrique ALBEROLA, Prof. | Banco de España, Spain
Mustafa AYDIN, Prof. | Kadir Has University, Turkey
Ian BACHE, Prof. | University of Sheffield, UK
Kee-Hong BAE, Prof. | York University, Canada
Mark BASSIN, Prof. | Sodertorn University, Sweden
Alexander BELLAMY, Prof. | Uni. of Queensland, Australia
Richard BELLAMY, Prof. | Uni. College London, UK
Andreas BIELER, Prof. | University of Nottingham, UK
Pinar BILGIN, Prof. | Bilkent University, Turkey
Ken BOOTH, Prof. | Aberystwyth University, UK
Stephen CHAN, Prof. | SOAS, University of London, UK
Nazli CHOUCRI, Prof. | MIT, USA
Judith CLIFTON, Prof. | Universidad de Cantabria, Spain
John M. DUNN, Prof. | University of Cambridge, UK
Kevin DUNN, Prof. | Hobart and William Smith Colleges, USA
Can ERBIL, Assoc. Prof. | Boston College, USA
Stephen Van EVERA, Prof. | MIT, USA
Marc FLEURBAEY, Prof. | Princeton University, USA
Bulent GOKAY, Prof. | Keele University, UK
Ayla GOL, Prof. | York St John University, UK
Stefano GUZZINI, Prof. | Uppsala Universitet, Sweden

David HELD, Prof. | London Sch. of Economics, LSE, UK
Tony HERON, Prof. | University of York, UK
Raymond HINNEBUSCH, Prof. | Uni. of St Andrews, UK
John M. HOBSON, Prof. | University of Sheffield, UK
Michael KENNY, Prof. | University of Sheffield, UK
Cécile LABORDE, Prof. | University College London, UK
Scott LUCAS, Prof. | University of Birmingham, UK
Kalypto NICOLAIDIS, Prof. | University of Oxford, UK
Ziya ONIS, Prof. | Koc University, Turkey
Alp OZERDEM, Prof. | George Mason University, USA
Danny QUAH, Prof. | London School of Economics, UK
José Gabriel PALMA, Prof. | Cambridge University, UK
Jenik RADON, Prof. | Columbia University, USA
Oliver RICHMOND, Prof. | University of Manchester, UK
Ibrahim SIRKECI, Prof. | Regent's College London, UK
Ian TAYLOR, Prof. | University of St Andrews, UK
Ali WATSON, Prof. | University of St Andrews, UK
Brian WHITE, Prof. | University of Sheffield, UK
Stefan WOLFF, Prof. | University of Birmingham, UK
Biol YESILADA, Prof. | Portland State University, USA
Hakan YILMAZKUDAY, Prof. | Florida International University, USA

The Rest: Journal of Politics and Development is published on behalf of the Centre for Strategic Research and Analysis (CESRAN) as an academic e-journal. The articles are brought into use via the website of the journal (<https://therestjournal.com/>). CESRAN and the Editors of The Rest: Journal of Politics and Development do not expect that readers of the review will sympathise with all the sentiments they find, for some of our writers will flatly disagree with others. It does not accept responsibility for the views expressed in any article, which appears in The Rest: Journal of Politics and Development.

** The surnames are listed in alphabetical order.*

the rest: journal of politics and development

Previously published as Journal of Global Analysis (JGA)

INDEXING & ABSTRACTING

- Academic Index
- Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE)
- Columbia International Affairs Online (CIAO)
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- EBSCO Publishing Inc.
- EconLit
- EconPapers
- Genamics JournalSeek
- IDEAS
- Index Islamicus
- Infomine
- International Bibliography of Book Reviews of Scholarly Literature in the Humanities and Social Sciences (IBR)
- International Bibliography of Periodical Literature in the Humanities and Social Sciences (IBZ)
- International Bibliography of the Social Sciences (IBSS)
- International Relations and Security Network (ISN)
- Lancaster Index to Defence & International Security Literature
- Peace Palace Library
- Research Papers in Economics (RePEc)
- Social Sciences Information Space (SOCIONET)
- Ulrich's Periodicals Directory

TABLE OF CONTENTS

RESEARCH ARTICLES

- 152** **India in a Changing Global Order: Geopolitical Challenges and Strategic Interests in the Indo-Myanmar Borderlands**
By Manashi Parashar
- 163** **The Evolution of Japan's Limited Sovereignty: From the Era of Unequal Treaties to the Japan-U.S. Alliance**
By Yukio Sakurai
- 182** **Liberty, Affect, and The Rise of Populism**
By Colin Anthony Smith MacNairn
- 198** **The Emergence of Hybrid Warfare and the Future of Global Security: A Comparative Study of Russian and NATO's Hybrid Infrastructure in Ukraine**
By Shahzada Rahim Abbas
- 213** **Implications of Military Aid on Global Arms Sales and Production**
By Zekeri Momoh
- 225** **A New Model for Measuring the Human Development Index: A Comparison of the Organisation of Turkic States and the EU**
By Abdullah Zübeyr Şekerci
- 245** **The Adaptation of Land Forces to the New Multipolar Order**
By Ricardo J Vieira
- 259** **Parliamentary Diplomacy and Ontological (In)Security in Small States**
By Nádia Teresa dos Santos
- 276** **Education and Africa's Structural Transformation: Human Capital, Partnerships, and the Case for a Pan-African Movement**
By Pedro Silva Baptista
- 298** **Revisiting Alexis de Tocqueville's Civil Society Concept from a Political-Economic Perspective**
By Ali Erdem Başçoban
- 311** **Overtourism: A Local and International Challenge to the Iberian Peninsula and Italy**
By Maria Antónia Pires de Almeida

International Think-tank www.cesran.org

Consultancy

Research Institute

CESRAN International is headquartered in the UK

CESRAN International is a member of the United Nations Academic Impact (UNAI)

CESRAN International is a think-tank specialising on international relations in general, and global peace, conflict and development related issues and challenges.

The main business objective/function is that we provide expertise at an international level to a wide range of policy making actors such as national governments and international organisations. CESRAN with its provisions of academic and semi-academic publications, journals and a fully-functioning website has already become a focal point of expertise on strategic research and analysis with regards to global security and peace. The Centre is particularly unique in being able to bring together wide variety of expertise from different countries and academic disciplines.

The main activities that CESRAN undertakes are providing consultancy services and advice to public and private enterprises, organising international conferences and publishing academic material.

Some of CESRAN's current publications are:

- THE REST: Journal of Politics and Development (tri-annual, peer reviewed) www.therestjournal.com
- Novus Orbis: Journal of Politics and International Relations (biannual, peer reviewed) www.dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/novusorbis
- Journal of Conflict Transformation and Security (biannual, peer reviewed)
- Political Reflection Magazine (quarterly) www.politicalreflectionmagazine.com (2010-2023)
- CESRAN Paper Series
- CESRAN Policy Brief
- Turkey Focus Policy Brief

CESRAN International also organises an annual international conference since 2014. Until 2023 it was called as “International Conference on Eurasian Politics and Society (IEPAS)”. From 2023, it was renamed as “CESRAN: Annual Conference on International Studies”.

<https://cesranconference.org/>

- **Ranked among the top 150 International think tanks**

The Evolution of Japan's Limited Sovereignty: From the Era of Unequal Treaties to the Japan-U.S. Alliance

the rest:
journal of politics and development
2025 | vol 15(2) | 163-181
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16882173
www.therestjournal.com

Yukio Sakurai

Dr., Yokohama National University, Japan
yukio1887@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1273-9227>

KEYWORDS

Autonomy,
Sovereignty,
Unequal treaties,
Japan-U.S. Security Treaty,
Japan-U.S. Status of
Forces Agreement (SOFA),
Japan-U.S. Security
Consultative Committee

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the evolution of Japan's limited sovereignty across two distinct historical periods: the nineteenth-century era of unequal treaties and the post-World War II era shaped by the Japan–U.S. alliance. In the earlier period, treaties imposed by Western powers curtailed Japan's jurisdictional and tariff autonomy. Paradoxically, these constraints catalysed rapid modernisation and a national drive to restore sovereign equality. In contrast, the post-war period introduced a different model of limited sovereignty: one characterised by strategic dependence through the Japan–U.S. Security Treaty and the Status of Forces Agreement (SOFA). These legal arrangements grant the United States significant military rights on Japanese territory, including base maintenance and jurisdictional authority, raising ongoing concerns about Japan's territorial and legal autonomy. Further tensions arise from the opaque operation of the Japan–U.S. Security Consultative Committee, whose limited transparency and perceived imbalance in representation have prompted criticism regarding undue U.S. influence. Evolving regional security dynamics and potential shifts in U.S. foreign policy further complicate Japan's sovereignty posture. Additionally, growing secrecy surrounding national security and the technical nature of defence policy hinder public deliberation and raise broader questions about democratic accountability. Employing an interdisciplinary framework that draws from international law, political science, and history, this study analyses the legal instruments and socio-political contexts that shaped these two periods. By comparing externally imposed and internally accepted constraints on sovereignty, the paper contributes to a deeper understanding of how nations negotiate autonomy within global power structures. This analysis, grounded in a comprehensive review of English and Japanese scholarship, offers a nuanced perspective on Japan's evolving relationship with limited sovereignty and its implications for democratic governance and strategic positioning in East Asia.

Received January 19, 2025

Revised July 10, 2025

Accepted July 16, 2025

Introduction

National sovereignty, nation-building, reconstruction, and national consciousness are key concepts for understanding the formation and evolution of modern states. These elements are closely interrelated, shaping both the development of state institutions and the construction of national identity. Among them, national sovereignty occupies a central place, referring to a state's supreme authority to govern its internal affairs without external interference (Odaka, 1984). It is grounded in

the classical doctrine that a state consists of three fundamental components: a defined territory, a permanent population, and sovereign authority (Odaka, 1984).

Japan's nineteenth-century experience with unequal treaties, imposed by Western imperial powers, directly challenged its territorial integrity, legal autonomy, and economic independence. The post-World War II era of limited sovereignty, while also constraining national autonomy, arose from a significantly different historical and geopolitical context. Shaped by the Cold War and Japan's continued security dependence on the U.S., this era's constraints primarily focused on defence and foreign policy, notably formalised through the Japan-U.S. Security Treaty and related agreements (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan, 2025).

These two distinct cases of limited sovereignty in Japan offer valuable insights into how states navigate within a system of unequal power. The concept itself reflects complex international dynamics. Formally recognised sovereign states frequently encounter constraints on their autonomy, arising from diverse internal and external sources, including economic dependence, military alliances, political pressure, and participation in international organisations. Japan's experience is not unique. Throughout history, numerous states have experienced limitations on their sovereignty.

The purpose of this paper is to analyse the complex and enduring issue of Japan's limited sovereignty as it has manifested across two critical historical periods: the nineteenth-century era of unequal treaties and the post-World War II period of constrained sovereignty under the Japan-U.S. alliance. By examining how Japan has navigated these externally imposed and internally accepted limitations, the paper explores their implications for the country's international standing, domestic policy, and evolving national identity.

Examining the legal instruments and agreements defining these periods and analysing their socio-political contexts, this study offers a nuanced understanding of sovereignty's multifaceted nature and the challenges of balancing power, security, and autonomy. Specifically, this paper explores Japan's adaptations to limited sovereignty, demonstrating how constraints have been transformed into opportunities for growth, influence, and national identity. This analysis offers a novel, comparative perspective on the evolution of sovereignty.

Theoretical background

In political theory, sovereignty is defined as the ultimate authority within a political community to make binding decisions and maintain internal order. As one of the most contested and multifaceted concepts in political science and international law, sovereignty intersects with the broader ideas of statehood, governance, independence, and democracy (Tagami, 1962; Britannica, n.d.). Stephen Krasner (1999) provides a foundational typology by identifying four distinct yet overlapping dimensions of sovereignty: international legal sovereignty (formal recognition by other states), Westphalian sovereignty (non-intervention and territorial autonomy), domestic sovereignty (the ability to control internal affairs), and interdependence sovereignty (regulation of cross-border flows). This framework allows for a more nuanced understanding of how sovereignty operates in practice and under constraints.

In the case of Japan, international legal sovereignty and Westphalian sovereignty are of particular relevance, as they highlight the complex tensions between formal recognition and external pressures that limit Japan's autonomous decision-making. While domestic and interdependence sovereignty are less directly applicable to the primary argument, they provide important contextual background for assessing the evolving nature of sovereignty in a globalised and interdependent world.

Within the field of international relations, sovereignty is frequently constrained by asymmetrical power dynamics, strategic alliances, and institutional dependencies. This phenomenon—commonly referred to as *limited sovereignty*—describes situations in which states, despite formal recognition and legal independence, face restrictions on their ability to exercise sovereign powers fully. These constraints can affect critical areas such as defence, foreign policy, economic governance, and domestic legal autonomy (Loughlin, 2017).

Importantly, *limited sovereignty* is distinct from the status of unrecognised states, which lack international legal standing, or collapsed states, which suffer from institutional breakdown and ineffective governance (Krasner, 2004). In this paper, *limited sovereignty* refers specifically to states that hold international legal sovereignty but experience partial limitations due to historical, geopolitical, or institutional factors.

The concept of *limited sovereignty* is evident in both historical and contemporary contexts. During the Cold War, the Brezhnev Doctrine asserted the Soviet Union's right to intervene in other socialist countries. This doctrine severely restricted the sovereignty of Eastern European nations. In another setting, many developing states continue to face limitations on their economic sovereignty. These constraints often stem from structural dependence on international financial institutions such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank.

A further example can be seen in the case of European Union (EU) member states. Although these states retain formal sovereignty, they participate in a form of pooled or shared sovereignty. Legislative and regulatory powers are transferred to supranational institutions to enable collective policymaking and implementation. These examples show that sovereignty is not an absolute or unchanging condition. Instead, it is shaped by historical, geopolitical, and institutional factors. As a result, sovereignty remains a flexible and context-dependent concept, with significant consequences for national interests, policy autonomy, and domestic governance (Krasner, 2001).

Methodology

This study examines Japan's experience of limited sovereignty across two distinct historical periods: the pre-war era of unequal treaties and the post-war era shaped by the Japan–U.S. alliance. Each period is analysed through its legal instruments and agreements that defined sovereignty constraints, as well as its broader socio-political context, including prevailing global power dynamics. A comparative analysis follows, highlighting the enduring implications for Japan's political development, foreign relations, and domestic governance. The conclusion synthesises the key findings.

The central research question guiding this study is: *How have externally imposed and internally accepted constraints on sovereignty in two key historical periods—Japan's pre-war era of unequal treaties and the post-war U.S.-Japan alliance—shaped the trajectory of Japan's political autonomy and international positioning?* This question drives comparative inquiry and underpins the selection of sources, analytical framework, and interpretive lens.

An interdisciplinary approach is employed, drawing on insights from international law, political science, history, and sociology. This framework enables a multifaceted examination of the evolution and consequences of Japan's limited sovereignty. A comprehensive literature review was conducted using both English and Japanese sources, incorporating scholarly works, legal texts, historical archives, and contemporary policy analyses. This methodological integration allows for a nuanced analysis that situates legal constraints within their broader historical and political contexts.

The research process focused on key terms such as “Japan–U.S. Security Treaty,” “limited sovereignty,” and “unequal treaties,” complemented by related concepts including “extraterritoriality,” “Japan–U.S. Status of Forces Agreement (SOFA),” “Japan–U.S. Security Consultative Committee,” and “tariff autonomy.” Searches were conducted through major academic databases and repositories, including Google Scholar, the University of Tokyo Library, and the National Diet Library of Japan, to identify relevant journal articles, books, government documents, and legal databases.

Unlike previous studies that examine the nineteenth-century and post-war sovereignty limitations in isolation, this study adopts a comparative framework that analyses both periods through the shared lens of limited sovereignty. The analysis differentiates these periods by the nature of the constraints—legal, economic, or military—and by whether these limitations were externally imposed or internally accepted.

While theoretical and contextual challenges are acknowledged, this comparative approach is crucial for understanding the contemporary manifestations of constrained sovereignty. It highlights how the legacies of nineteenth-century arrangements continue to shape present-day debates on Japan's autonomy. Moreover, it points to the possibility of future sovereignty challenges, suggesting that evolving geopolitical and institutional dynamics may again test Japan's capacity for independent decision-making.

The Unequal Treaties and Their Impact on Japan

Extraterritoriality and tariff restrictions

The mid-nineteenth century marked a watershed moment in Japanese history. The nation's long-held policy of seclusion (*sakoku*) was abruptly ended by the arrival of Western imperial powers. Admiral Matthew C. Perry's (1794–1858) forceful entry into Edo Bay in July 1853 with four armed ships, including two steam-powered vessels, followed by his second visit with nine armed ships, including three steam-powered vessels, signalled the end of Japan's self-imposed isolation and the beginning of its engagement with the modern world. However, this engagement was far from equal.

Confronted with the overwhelming military and technological superiority of Western powers, such as the armed steam-powered vessels equipped with many canons, Japan was compelled to enter into a series of treaties that significantly compromised its sovereignty. These treaties, beginning with the 1854 Treaty of Kanagawa with the U.S. (Office of The Historian, 1853) and extending to the commercial treaties of 1858, became known as “unequal treaties.” These agreements not only facilitated foreign trade in Japanese ports but also established extraterritoriality and imposed substantial limitations on Japan's tariff autonomy, thus severely restricting its sovereignty.

During the nineteenth-century age of imperialism, international law categorised the world according to a Western-defined “standard of civilisation,” classifying nations as “civilised,” “semi-civilised,” and “uncivilised” (Mälksoo, 2017; Shahabuddin, 2019). While these terms are now recognised as inappropriate and discriminatory, they were historically used to categorise states. “Civilised” denoted sovereign states, “semi-civilised” designated states with limited sovereignty, and “uncivilised” referred to colonies. European nations and the U.S. were deemed “civilised,” while Japan, under the then-prevailing Eurocentric legal framework, was classified as “semi-civilised” (Sakurai, 2023).

The prevailing legal principle held that “civilised” nations possessed the right to apply their laws extraterritorially. This meant that their citizens would not be subject to legal systems deemed “semi-civilised,” such as traditional Japanese trials lacking legal representation, or punishments

considered brutal, like torture. This historical legal reasoning stemmed from the perceived absence of European-style legal systems in Japan (Sakurai, 2023). Japan's acceptance of extraterritoriality for "civilised" peoples (i.e., the application of, for example, English law outside of England) was coupled with the renunciation of tariff autonomy in treaties with foreign powers, including the U.S., the Netherlands, Russia, Great Britain, and France.

The implications of extraterritoriality and the loss of tariff autonomy imposed by the unequal treaties were profound. Extraterritoriality, a legal principle granting foreign nationals' immunity from local laws, meant that foreigners residing in Japan were subject to the jurisdiction of their own consular courts, not Japanese law. This provision undermined Japan's legal sovereignty and created a situation of legal asymmetry, where foreigners enjoyed privileges and immunities not afforded to Japanese citizens. This system effectively established foreign enclaves within Japan, where Westerners operated outside Japanese legal authority, further eroding Japan's control over its territory and population.

The loss of tariff autonomy, which prevented Japan from establishing its own import and export tariffs, had equally profound economic effects. Japan was unable to protect its nascent domestic industries from competition with cheaper foreign goods. For instance, within the textile sector, Japanese silk and cotton producers experienced diminished competitiveness against British and American imports. This constraint hampered industrial development, fostered economic dependence on Western powers, and restricted the government's revenue generation capacity, thereby further limiting its fiscal sovereignty.

The Tokugawa Shogunate's Initial Response

During the 1850s and 1860s, Japan was governed by the Tokugawa Shogunate, a hereditary ruling system headed by a Shogun (the supreme military and political leader) from the Tokugawa family, which had held power since 1603 (Sakurai, 2023). A defining characteristic of the Tokugawa Shogunate was its policy of national seclusion, implemented between 1633 and 1854. This policy restricted foreign interaction to limited, authorised trade with Dutch merchants at the designated enclave of Dejima in Nagasaki.

Consequently, even high-ranking officials within the Tokugawa Shogunate possessed limited knowledge of foreign countries and lacked knowledge of modern legal systems and international law at the time of treaty negotiations. Indeed, it was not until discussions with Townsend Harris, the American consul-general, in 1857 that they gained a rudimentary understanding of international legal principles.

Recognising this deficiency, the Tokugawa Shogunate dispatched two young officials, Amane Nishi (1829–1897) and Masamichi Tsuda (1829–1903), to the Netherlands in the early summer of 1863 to study modern law (Nagao, 1979, n.d.; Sakurai, 2023). There, they dedicated themselves to learning Dutch until 1865, attending twice-weekly lectures at the residence of Leiden University Professor Simon Fisseling (1818–1888). Their studies encompassed five key areas: natural law (primarily civil law), international law, constitutional law, economics, and statistics.

Upon their return, these two officials served as advisors to the last Shogun, Yoshinobu Tokugawa, and subsequently published treatises on law. However, the immediate impact of these publications was limited due to the subsequent collapse of the Tokugawa Shogunate. In 1867, Yoshinobu Tokugawa relinquished his position as Shogun and pledged allegiance to the emperor. The following year, the Meiji Restoration restructured governance, centralising authority under imperial rule. In 1869, the emperor was transferred from Kyoto to Tokyo, marking a symbolic shift in power.

The Struggle for Treaty Revision by the New Government

A primary objective for the leaders of Japan in the newly established government was the rapid transformation of the country into an internationally recognised modern sovereign state (Sakurai, 2023). This objective spurred a strong impetus for modernisation, with the establishment of a modern legal system and the adoption of a parliamentary system considered essential foundations. To inform this process, the Iwakura Mission was established. This was headed by Tomomi Iwakura (1825–1883) and involved a comprehensive round-the-world tour between November 1871 and September 1873.

The aim of this mission was to research various nations to identify suitable models for Japan's modernisation, in addition to conducting official diplomatic visits on behalf of the new government. The Iwakura Mission, a delegation of approximately 150 officials, undertook a diplomatic tour of twelve countries, including the U.S., Great Britain, France, Russia, Germany, Austria, and Italy. The mission engaged in discussions with the leaders of these countries, meticulously documenting their diplomatic activities and observations. The mission submitted detailed reports to the Japanese government, providing a comprehensive account of their experiences and observations (Japan Centre for Asian Historical Records, 2018).

Following the tour, Iwakura concluded that Germany, as a rising imperial power, offered the most suitable model for a modernising Japan. The mission members were particularly impressed by Chancellor Otto von Bismarck (1815–1898) and the seemingly harmonious relationship between the Kaiser and the Chancellor, viewing Germany as a potential blueprint for a future Japanese empire. This admiration for Germany significantly influenced the drafting of the 1889 Constitution, the 1898 Civil Code, and other legal instruments, which drew heavily from German legal principles (Sakurai, 2023).

However, the Japanese government strategically adopted a diversified approach to modernisation, drawing inspiration from various nations. For example, railway and road infrastructure, along with the postal system, were modelled after British examples; law, medical science, and military organisation drew heavily from Germany; engineering and shipbuilding techniques were adopted from Scotland; and the bureaucratic system and administrative law were inspired by France. This diversified approach to modernisation reflects a deliberate Japanese policy to avoid over-reliance on any single foreign power, driven by a paramount concern for national independence and preventing potential domination.

Reclaiming Autonomy after 57 Years

To achieve modernisation and recognition as a "civilised" nation by Western-defined international legal standards, Japan implemented substantial reforms, including the establishment of a modern legal system and a parliamentary system, alongside concurrent militarisation and industrialisation efforts. Subsequently, the Japanese government initiated a systematic process of treaty revision negotiations with the U.S., Great Britain, and other relevant nations.

This long-term effort gradually led to revisions in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. Through diplomatic efforts, coupled with Japan's demonstrable progress in modernisation and its growing military strength, the Western powers eventually agreed to treaty revision. The abolition of extraterritoriality in 1899 significantly restored Japan's jurisdictional sovereignty. The restoration of full tariff autonomy in 1911 further liberated Japan from the economic constraints imposed by the treaties, enabling independent economic policymaking.

This treaty revision process became intertwined with broader projects of nation-building and modernisation, even as Japan simultaneously emerged as an imperial power, extending its rule over neighbouring territories, including Taiwan (1895) and the Korean Peninsula (1910). These achievements marked a turning point in Japanese history, signifying the restoration of national sovereignty and paving the way for Japan's emergence as a major power. The period of significant limitations on sovereignty that Japan experienced as a result of the unequal treaties has been commonly viewed as a powerful catalyst for national transformation.

Japan's experience of unequal treatment by Western powers fostered a strong desire to overcome externally imposed limitations. Nationalistic sentiment, along with the practical need to revise unequal treaties, became a key driver of Japan's modernisation. This is reflected in the country's rapid industrialisation, military expansion, and social reforms. Diplomacy alone did not lead to treaty revision. Japan was also forced to engage in costly wars and large-scale national mobilisation to gain recognition from Western powers. It sought to be acknowledged as a "civilised" nation under the standards of international law at the time.

The pursuit of treaty revision came at significant military and financial cost. Japan fought two major wars: against China (1894–1895) and Russia (1904–1905), resulting in over 100,000 deaths. The expenses far exceeded Japan's annual national budget. The Russo-Japanese War alone cost approximately ten times the annual budget and left the country burdened with long-term debt. War debt repayment began in 1906 and continued until 1986. The legacy of unequal treaties is complex. While they initially constrained Japan's sovereignty and development, they also—paradoxically—spurred its transformation into a modern, powerful state (Shahabuddin, 2019).

The Era of Limited Sovereignty after the War

The Post-War Occupation Context

Japan's defeat in World War II and subsequent seven-year occupation between 1945 and 1952 by the Allied forces, primarily the U.S. under the Supreme Commander for the Allied Powers (SCAP), General Douglas MacArthur (1880–1964), marked a profound nadir in its national sovereignty (Nishi, 2005). The period of occupation, which lasted from September 1945 to April 1952, was initially characterised by stringent demilitarisation and democratization policies. Under the direction of the SCAP, Japan underwent a fundamental transformation, with sweeping reforms reshaping its political, economic, and social landscape (Nishi, 2005).

These reforms encompassed substantial amendments to the Constitution, with the objective of establishing a pacifist and democratic framework; the restructuring of the education system, aimed at dismantling militaristic ideologies and promoting democratic values; the reform of the agricultural land ownership system, aimed at redistributing land and empowering farmers; the legalization and promotion of trade unions, aimed at empowering workers; and the reform of the family system, aimed at challenging traditional patriarchal structures. These reforms aimed to reshape Japanese society and establish the foundations for a democratic and peaceful nation. However, some scholars, such as Helen Mears (1948/2015), have argued that these reforms, particularly given the numerous strictures imposed on Japan, also reflected a degree of retribution for wartime actions.

A key element of continuity between the pre- and post-war periods was the retention of the existing Japanese bureaucracy. This bureaucracy, with its established structures and expertise, was deemed essential by the U.S. occupation forces to ensure the smooth administration of the country during the transition and to facilitate the implementation of the extensive reform programs. The

bureaucracy played a crucial role in supporting the U.S. occupation and the implementation of its transformative agenda.

The emergence of the Cold War and escalating tensions between the U.S. and the Soviet Union profoundly impacted the strategic landscape in the Far East. The U.S., increasingly concerned about the spread of communism, particularly after the Chinese Revolution of 1949 and the Korean War (1950–1953), began to view Japan not as a defeated enemy but as a vital strategic partner in its containment policy. This geopolitical shift led to a reassessment of U.S. occupation policy, paving the way for the eventual restoration of Japanese sovereignty.

Treaty of San Francisco and the Japan-U.S. Security Treaty

On 8 September 1951, the Treaty of San Francisco 1951 formally restored Japan's sovereignty, marking the official conclusion of the Allied occupation in 1952 (Tanaka, n.d.). However, this restoration of formal independence was inextricably linked to the simultaneous signing of the Treaty of Mutual Cooperation and Security between the United States and Japan of 1951. This bilateral agreement, focused on the stationing of U.S. Forces Japan (USFJ) for the maintenance of international peace and security in the Far East, became the foundation for Japan's post-war security policy (Office of the Historian, 1952).

The treaty provided Japan with a crucial security guarantee, particularly in the volatile context of the Cold War, but also imposed significant constraints on Japan's military autonomy (Office of the Historian, 1952). Article 9 (Renunciation of War) of the Constitution, heavily influenced by the occupation authorities and renouncing war as an instrument of national policy, coupled with the security treaty, constitutionally restricted Japan's ability to develop a fully independent and robust military capability. While the treaty was instrumental in providing security, it simultaneously constrained Japan's defence policy autonomy.

The 1960 revision of the Japan-U.S. Security Treaty marked a pivotal moment in its evolution, signifying a shift toward a more equitable partnership. Key changes included a clear U.S. commitment to defend Japan (Article V), requiring prior U.S. consultation with Japan before deploying forces from Japanese bases for operations outside of Japan, and a revised Status of Forces Agreement (SOFA) clarifying the legal status of U.S. forces. These revisions strengthened Japan's security, increased reciprocity in the alliance, and solidified the treaty as the cornerstone of Japan's defence policy, shaping its security posture and its relationship with the U.S. for decades to come.

While the treaty has been subject to various interpretations and debates over the decades, it is evident that the post-war security arrangement with the U.S. has been instrumental in providing crucial stability for Japan, facilitating its remarkable economic resurgence. This stability, while requiring adjustments in Japan's defence posture, has allowed the nation to focus on economic development and cultivate its diplomatic influence. This long-term continuity underscores the enduring impact of the initial post-war settlement on Japan's sovereignty and its place in the international system (Green and Cronin, 1999; Green, 2010; Oros, n.d.).

The Japan-U.S. Status of Forces Agreement (SOFA)

The Status of Forces Agreement (SOFA), a pivotal legal instrument accompanying the Security Treaty, further delineates the practical implications of the security arrangement and codifies the limitations on Japan's territorial and legal sovereignty (Aketagawa, 1999; 2017; Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan, 2024). The SOFA delineates the legal status and operational modalities of the U.S. military within Japan, thereby granting the U.S. military the right to maintain bases and facilities

throughout the country. This right constitutes a significant encroachment on Japan's territorial integrity, extending beyond mere physical presence.

For instance, the U.S. air base at Yokota, among others, influences Japan's management of the greater Tokyo airspace, raising questions about the nation's capacity to independently manage its air traffic and security (Yabe, 2017). These restrictions, while not explicitly codified in Japanese law, appear to stem from *de facto* arrangements during the occupation, later formalised as a 'temporary measure' in the 1952 agreement based on the SOFA (The Mainichi, 2019; Yoshida, 2016). The restoration of control over the Yokota airspace has been a subject of ongoing discussion in the Diet; however, substantive progress toward this objective has yet to be made.

Furthermore, the agreement addressed complex jurisdictional issues, particularly concerning criminal jurisdiction, frequently granting U.S. military personnel and civilian employees associated with the military exemptions from Japanese law in specific circumstances. This provision has been a persistent source of tension and legal debate, raising questions about the extent of Japan's legal sovereignty and its ability to exercise full control over its territory and the individuals within it. Notably, incidents involving U.S. military personnel, even those deemed unlawful, have frequently remained unresolved under Japanese law, intensifying public concern about the limitations imposed by the SOFA (Office of the Historian, 1957a; 1957b).

The agreement also delineated various administrative aspects of the U.S. military presence, including entry and exit procedures, customs regulations, taxation, and claims for damages arising from U.S. military activities. These provisions, while arguably necessary for the practical functioning of the alliance, further solidified the limitations on Japan's sovereign control and underscored the complex legal and administrative framework underpinning the constrained nature of its sovereignty (Fujiu, 2024). A notable aspect of the SOFA is the grant of authority to the U.S. to establish and maintain bases across Japan without explicit limitations, which grants a substantial degree of influence on the U.S. and potentially compromises local autonomy and land use rights (Yabe, 2017).

The Japan-U.S. Security Consultative Committee

The Japan-U.S. Security Consultative Committee, established in accordance with the SOFA, serves as the primary forum for bilateral discussions regarding the U.S. military presence in Japan (Yoshida, 2016). Comprised of representatives from both governments, this committee is entrusted with the responsibility of addressing operational issues, resolving disputes, and ensuring the seamless functioning of the security arrangement. The Committee's contribution to security policies has been the subject of considerable recognition. However, the committee's deliberations and transparency have been subject to scrutiny, with a key point of contention related to the Committee's composition (Yoshida, 2016).

The Japanese delegation comprises high-ranking government officials from ministries under the purview of the Director-General of the North American Affairs Bureau at the Japanese Ministry of Foreign Affairs. In contrast, the U.S. delegation consists of U.S. military officers and the Minister at the U.S. Embassy in Japan, led by the Deputy Commander of USFJ. Consequently, the Joint Committee's deliberations and resolutions are not conducted through official diplomatic channels between the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan and the U.S. Embassy in Japan (Department of State). This raises concerns regarding the level of diplomatic oversight and the potential for military considerations to supersede broader political and diplomatic concerns.

Critics contend that the committee's closed proceedings impede transparency. The minutes of the Joint Committee have not been made public since 1952, except for eighty-four pieces of joint statements accessible on the Ministry of Foreign Affairs website (The Diet, 2022; Ministry of Foreign

Affairs of Japan, 2024a). This is due to the 1960 Committee's agreement that the official minutes of the Committee are considered official documents concerning both governments and are not published unless agreed by both parties. Therefore, the Japanese public is largely uninformed regarding the specifics of discussions and agreements that considerably impact their lives and national security.

During a Diet debate, Katsuya Okada, a member of the Diet and former foreign minister, commented: "I consider the agreement reached between a director at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the deputy commander of the U.S. Forces Japan to be highly inappropriate. This is because it overrides the 2001 Information Disclosure Act and the 2009 Public Records Management Act, which were enacted by the Diet." (The Diet, 2022). These legal instruments establish a framework that enables citizens to access government-held information and ensures the proper management of public records. The absence of transparency, in conjunction with the perceived imbalance in influence between the two parties, gives rise to concerns regarding Japan's capacity to effectively assert its national interests.

It has been argued that significant policy matters pertaining to the U.S. military presence in Japan are determined through non-transparent processes, thereby circumventing public scrutiny and democratic accountability. Consequently, while the Committee plays a vital role within the alliance framework, it also represents a potential channel for U.S. influence over Japanese defence and security policy. This underscores the subtle, yet substantial, constraints imposed on Japan's sovereignty within the alliance framework. Yoshida (2016) suggests that the Japan-U.S. Security Consultative Committee operates outside the purview of the Japanese Constitution. If substantiated, this would constitute a serious infringement on Japanese sovereignty.

Complexities of Limited Sovereignty

While post-war security arrangements with the U.S. facilitated Japan's economic prioritisation and subsequent growth, they also constrained aspects of its sovereignty, thus impacting Japan's autonomy. The following four examples illustrate typical disputes arising from this dynamic:

1. The 1957 Girard incident: A U.S. soldier killed a Japanese woman while on duty at a U.S. Army firing range, sparking a jurisdictional dispute under the SOFA. While the U.S. initially asserted jurisdiction, subsequent negotiations within the Japan-U.S. Committee led to the U.S. agreeing to allow Japan to prosecute. Girard was ultimately tried and convicted in a Japanese court, receiving a suspended sentence (Office of The Historian, 1957a; 1957b).
2. The 1959 Sunagawa case: Seven individuals were prosecuted for violating laws related to the Japan-U.S. Security Treaty by entering a U.S. military base during a protest. The Tokyo District Court acquitted them, citing the unconstitutionality of the U.S. military presence under Article 9 of the Constitution of Japan. However, the Supreme Court reversed this decision, ultimately convicting the defendants (Courts of Japan, n.d.). In doing so, the Supreme Court invoked the "act of state doctrine," arguing that highly political matters, such as the Security Treaty, are not subject to judicial review, thereby avoiding a direct constitutional ruling. Declassified U.S. documents, which were revealed in 2008 in the U.S., suggested prior informal discussions between the Chief Justice and the U.S. Ambassador (The Asahi Shimbun, 2024a).
3. The 1995 Okinawa Minor Rape Incident: This incident underscored the limitations of Japanese criminal jurisdiction under the SOFA, igniting public outrage and large-scale protests. The U.S. initially resisted handing over the suspects to Japanese authorities prior to indictment, citing provisions within the SOFA that, at the time, allowed U.S. military

personnel suspected of crimes to remain in U.S. custody. This stance further fueled criticism of the agreement. The case intensified calls for revising the SOFA to grant Japan greater judicial control, specifically regarding the custody and prosecution of U.S. military personnel accused of committing crimes on Japanese soil (Guinto, 2024).

4. **The Futenma Base Relocation Issue:** While the necessity of relocating the Futenma airbase is generally acknowledged due to safety and noise concerns, the ongoing debate surrounding the proposed relocation site in Henoko underscores a significant discord between local and national interests (The Asahi Shimbun, 2024b). The substantial financial burden associated with the Henoko construction project, coupled with persistent environmental concerns—particularly regarding the impact on the delicate marine ecosystem—and the complex interplay between national security imperatives and the desire for regional autonomy, highlights the multifaceted challenges inherent in attempting to reconcile national defence policies with the aspirations and concerns of local communities.

The publication of *Ryukyu Shimpo* (2004) found that USFJ facilities and areas numbered 135, occupying 0.27% of Japanese territory. The prefectures hosting the largest number of these facilities and areas, in descending order, were Okinawa (Area share in the prefecture:10.43%), Hokkaido (0.41%), Kanagawa (0.89%), Nagasaki (0.11%), and Hiroshima (0.06%), demonstrating the disproportionate concentration in Okinawa Prefecture. This concentration has led to significant local resentment and political activism. For the most current information on major USFJ facilities and areas, consult the Ministry of Defence website (Ministry of Defence of Japan, 2025).

The ongoing presence of U.S. military bases and the provisions of the SOFA have been a persistent source of domestic political debate, raising complex questions about the balance between national security, local concerns, and the extent of Japan's effective sovereignty. These debates frequently centre on issues of base relocation, environmental impact, the legal status of U.S. military personnel, and the disproportionate burden borne by Okinawa. These issues underscore the ongoing tension between the perceived benefits and the tangible constraints of Japan's security dependence and its implications for national sovereignty, despite the apparent lack of readily available resolutions.

Current Security Situation in the Far East

In the wake of post-Cold War shifts in the international landscape, particularly the rise of China, the Japan-U.S. alliance has evolved into a more deeply cooperative partnership, with an expanded role for Japan. The Japan-U.S. security framework has shifted from a relationship of dependency to one of collaboration, influencing Japan's standing within the global community. Through strategic adaptation and sustained diplomatic efforts, Japan has progressively transformed the alliance from a potential constraint on its autonomy into a platform for regional leadership and cooperation.

The Japan-U.S. 2+2 Ministerial Meetings, a key platform for bilateral dialogue between the Foreign and Defence Ministers, facilitate addressing evolving security challenges and pursuing shared strategic objectives. These meetings have fostered enhanced security cooperation. Furthermore, the July 1, 2014, reinterpretation of Article 9 of the Constitution, previously limiting Japan to individual self-defence, now permits collective self-defence. This shift, coupled with increased military integration, raises concerns about Japan's potential involvement in broader regional conflicts. The framework of security cooperation has expanded to encompass the Indo-Pacific region, including bilateral initiatives with Australia, India, and Vietnam.

The continued presence of U.S. forces in South Korea still remains crucial for regional stability. A significant reduction in the U.S. military presence could necessitate a fundamental reassessment of security strategies by all East Asian nations, including Japan. This scenario presents a considerable

military and diplomatic challenge, requiring a thorough examination of potential power vacuums, regional rivalries, and the future of the Japan-U.S. alliance. Such a substantial shift highlights the inherent vulnerability of Japan's security posture under its current framework of limited sovereignty.

The recent U.S. administration's policies, including protectionist trade measures and a reduced commitment to international alliances, have introduced potential uncertainties into the Far Eastern security landscape. Possible shifts in U.S. foreign policy, particularly concerning military commitments and alliance configurations, are a significant concern. Such shifts could have far-reaching consequences, potentially reshaping East Asian security dynamics and destabilising a region that has experienced relative peace since the Korean War armistice in 1953 (Ikenberry and Watanabe, 2024).

From the perspective of ordinary citizens, current national security policies are increasingly difficult to understand. This is especially true in areas such as defence capability development and the deepening integration of command-and-control systems between Japanese and U.S. forces for potential regional conflicts (Johnstone and Schoff, 2024). Two main factors contribute to this complexity: limited public access to security-related information and the highly technical nature of the subject matter. As a result, understanding is largely confined to experts, and opportunities for meaningful citizen participation in national security debates and policymaking remain limited, despite the critical importance of these issues.

Discussion

Comparison of Japan's Limited Sovereignty: Nineteenth Century vs. Post-war Era

Japan's pre-war and post-war experiences with limited sovereignty differ significantly in their origins, nature, and consequences. These divergent historical trajectories have given rise to a range of divergent scholarly interpretations. The pre-war era, marked by the imposition of unequal treaties by imperialist Western powers, represents a direct assault on Japan's sovereignty. This was legally binding and resulted in the infringement of fundamental sovereign rights. This era, characterised by economic exploitation and legal subjugation, nevertheless catalysed a powerful drive for modernisation and national self-strengthening.

Akira Irie and Kenneth Pyle emphasise that Japan's deliberate and strategic modernisation was instrumental in overcoming the challenges posed by the treaties and in establishing its position as a sovereign nation in the international community (Irie, 1966; Pyle, 1996). Japan's experience with limited sovereignty fuelled a national drive for equality with Western powers. This impetus spurred rapid industrialisation, military expansion, and legal reforms, all designed to demonstrate Japan's capacity to be a modern, "civilised" nation by Western-defined international legal standards (Pyle, 1996).

Japan's pursuit of recognition and autonomy ultimately contributed to its own imperial ambitions, a complex and ultimately tragic consequence of its earlier experience with limited sovereignty. This interpretation aligns with the concept of a "reactive state" (Calder, 1988), which posits that external pressure and perceived threats to national identity can lead to a heightened sense of insecurity and a desire to assert national power. This orientation also stemmed from the pragmatic and ideological motivations of political leaders to facilitate national modernisation and integrate internal debates.

In contrast, the post-war era's limited sovereignty stemmed from the security alliance with the U.S. following the seven-year occupation, a markedly distinct context. While the unequal treaties were imposed by external powers against Japan's will, the post-war security arrangements were, in a sense, chosen by Japan, albeit within the constraints of its defeat and occupation. As Mears

(1948/2015) explores, the initial period of occupation represented a profound disruption of Japanese sovereignty, with the Allied Forces, particularly the U.S., exerting significant control over Japan's political, economic, and social institutions.

However, the evolving Cold War context led to a shift in U.S. policy, transforming Japan from a defeated enemy into a crucial strategic partner. The Japan-U.S. Security Treaty, while constraining Japan's military autonomy, also furnished a pivotal security umbrella that enabled Japan to prioritise economic reconstruction and development. In the post-war period, Japan's sovereignty was constrained by the ideological imperatives of the Cold War and the context of "chosen" limitations.

Rather than being characterised by direct legal restrictions on core sovereign powers as seen in the unequal treaties, this period was marked by a strategic reliance on the U.S. for security, which in turn influenced Japan's foreign policy and its capacity to act independently in international affairs. The limitations were thus less explicit, more embedded in the structure of the security relationship, and arguably more beneficial in the short term, though potentially limiting in the long run. This viewpoint is consistent with the prevailing narrative that Japan's security dependence was solely a strategic choice rather than a constraint.

This aligns with the observations of scholars Masataka Kosaka (1968, 2006) and Hiroshi Nakanishi (2010), who emphasised the crucial role of the U.S. security guarantee in enabling Japan's economic revitalisation. This strategy, often termed the "Yoshida Doctrine" after Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida (1878–1967), placed significant emphasis on Japan's reliance on the U.S. for security and strategically leveraged post-war constraints to prioritise economic growth (Kosaka, 1968, 2006; Nakanishi, 2010).

The nature of the imposed limitations differed significantly. The unequal treaties focused on economic and legal restrictions, directly affecting Japan's ability to regulate its own trade, administer its justice system, and participate equally in the international legal order. In contrast, the post-war limitations were oriented toward security and defence, impeding Japan's capacity to develop a fully independent military and pursue an autonomous foreign policy. This discrepancy can be attributed to the shifting priorities of the international system.

In the nineteenth century, the primary concerns were trade, legal recognition, and territorial control. In the post-war era, national security, particularly in the context of the Cold War, became the dominant concern. The Japan-U.S. alliance became a cornerstone of U.S. security policy in the Far East, shaping Japan's strategic options and influencing its relationships with other regional actors. This paradigm shift was codified in the 1960 conclusion of the Japan-U.S. Security Treaty, which accentuated mutual cooperation and security between the two nations.

These two periods of limited sovereignty also had distinct impacts on Japanese society (see Chart 1). The unequal treaties era fostered a keen sense of national grievance and a determination to overcome imposed limitations, fueling modernisation and contributing to Japan's rise as a major power (Irie, 1966). Moreover, the experience of these unequal treaties shaped Japan's understanding of international relations, fostering a belief in the importance of national strength and self-reliance (Irie, 1966).

The post-war period witnessed significant controversy and opposition to the Japan-U.S. Security Treaty, particularly in the 1950s and 1960s, reflecting anxieties about Japanese sovereignty. However, subsequent decades have seen greater public acceptance of the alliance's constraints. This shift is partly due to the tangible benefits from the U.S. security umbrella, including peace and economic prosperity. From a cost-benefit perspective, Japan has strategically leveraged the alliance,

deriving substantial advantages that arguably outweigh its sovereignty limitations. While the SOFA presents operational challenges and requires continuous dialogue, it also serves as a crucial mechanism for managing the alliance's evolving dynamics and reflects Japan's growing assertiveness.

While a utilitarian perspective offers one lens for evaluating the alliance, it risks overlooking the potential erosion of essential elements of national identity. As generational memory of wartime experiences fades, public understanding of fundamental state principles and the significance of sovereignty may diminish. Revisiting these often-overlooked normative aspects and reaffirming the importance of national sovereignty for informed civic participation in the contemporary context seems imperative.

Japan's security dependence on the United States has significantly constrained its autonomy in foreign, monetary, and trade policy, while also shaping its national identity. As the post-war global order shifts from U.S. hegemony toward a multipolar system, the ability to formulate independent policies becomes increasingly important. Such autonomy is vital for securing essential resources—including energy, food, and minerals—ensuring national stability and advancing self-determination. To navigate this transition and enhance its sovereignty, Japan must develop national strategies and cultivate human resources grounded in its own values and priorities.

Chart 1: Comparison of Japan's Limited Sovereignty: 19th Century vs. Postwar Era

Feature	Unequal Treaties Era (1854-1911, Treaty Revision Complete)	U.S. Occupation/Security Treaty (1945-Ongoing)
Primary Constraint	External legal restrictions	Security dependence on the U.S.
Source of Limitation	Western imperial powers	U.S. occupation, Cold War
Legal Basis	Unequal Treaties	Security Treaty, SOFA
Scope of Sovereignty Affected	Legal, territorial, and economic restrictions	Military and foreign policy constraints
Key Mechanisms	Extraterritoriality, tariff restrictions	U.S. bases, SOFA, and Security Consultative Committee arrangements
Geopolitical Context	Imperialism	Cold War and post-Cold War
Japan's Response	Modernisation, military buildup, and industrialisation	Economic focus, alliance with the U.S., reinterpretation of Article 9 and expansion of the self-defence forces
Consequences	Modernisation, great power status, shaped national identity and foreign policy outlook.	Economic prosperity, constrained military, ongoing debate on security dependence and national identity
Scholarly Views	Reactive nationalism, modernisation catalyst	Strategic dependence, "chosen" limitation, debate on democratic implications of U.S. dependence
Contemporary Issues	Legacy of unequal treaties and national identity	U.S. policy shifts, regional security, and debate on Article 9

Source: Author's compilation.

Prospect for the Future: Democratic Consensus

Japan has consistently deepened security cooperation with the U.S., pursuing mutual economic and strategic benefits while contributing to regional stability in the post-Cold War era (Sakurada, 1997).

This policy has been consistently reaffirmed by successive leaders in both countries. However, this security reliance constrains Japan's diplomatic autonomy. Specifically, it aligns Japan's foreign policy with the U.S., limits its independent military capacity, and raises questions about its territorial and legal sovereignty due to the U.S. military presence. This dependence impacts Japan's relationships with other nations and its ability to pursue fully independent diplomatic initiatives.

Jennifer Lind (2022) has questioned the long-term implications of this reliance for Japanese democracy and public engagement with national sovereignty and foreign policy. The ongoing debate surrounding Article 9 of the Japanese constitution underscores the persistent tension between Japan's pacifist identity and aspirations for a more conventional military posture. Fundamentally, Japan, as an independent nation, must autonomously consider its present and future based on established principles of state sovereignty.

Scholars such as Jeffrey Hornung (2019) and Terashima and Kurashige (2024) argue that Japan's current security framework, rooted in the post-war era, requires re-evaluation in light of today's geopolitical realities. The future of the Japan–U.S. alliance demands a transparent, forward-looking approach that emphasises accountability and is strategically integrated into broader initiatives, such as the “Free and Open Indo-Pacific” (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan, 2024b). Japan's participation in the QUAD (Australia, India, Japan, and the United States) reflects both its alignment with U.S. strategic priorities and its pursuit of sovereign hedging. Beyond the QUAD, Japan seeks to assert its sovereignty in navigating an increasingly volatile world order. However, its strategic autonomy remains constrained by shifting U.S. policies and escalating regional threats.

In practice, national security matters in Japan are often shielded from public scrutiny, a situation exacerbated by the 2013 Act on the Protection of Specially Designated Secrets. This act grants broad government discretion in classifying information and imposes severe penalties for leaks, fostering public scepticism and impeding informed public discourse on national security issues. This, in turn, hinders the democratic processes that the alliance is ostensibly intended to protect. This mechanism creates a dilemma for Japanese citizens: while national defence is a crucial issue, its complexities and lack of transparency place it beyond effective public oversight.

Japan's long-standing security dependence on the United States has deeply shaped its security identity. This reliance seems to have slowed the development of a clear understanding of sovereignty and independence, especially within the education system. It has also limited public debate on these fundamental concepts. As a result, a diminished sense of sovereignty may exist in Japanese society. Many citizens appear unaware of how their country's autonomy is restricted or what that means in practice. These constraints are often accepted without reflection on their origins or consequences. As Takashi Inoguchi (1998) argues, building a strong sense of sovereignty is a vital civic duty.

Looking ahead, a key long-term challenge is how to manage potential revisions to the Japan–U.S. Security Treaty and related agreements within the existing bilateral framework. While persistent obstacles remain, there is growing recognition of the need for greater transparency and public participation in security policymaking. These elements are essential not only to maintaining the strength of the alliance but also to upholding democratic values. This need is further underscored by the recurring shifts in U.S. foreign policy following presidential elections, which introduce uncertainty and demand that Japan remain adaptable while ensuring that its own democratic processes guide long-term strategic decisions.

A broader historical perspective—from 1854 to the present—provides critical insight into how such complexities have been addressed and how more equitable solutions might emerge. Public deliberation in both countries on the alliance's future is essential to achieving mutual benefit and lasting peace. Broad-based agreement on a fair and balanced framework enables citizens to hold

governments accountable and foster democratic consensus. This consensus is vital not only for future prosperity but also to uphold the alliance's normative foundations. These aspirations—rooted in transparency and mutual understanding—must be cultivated across generations to ensure that security does not come at the expense of democracy.

Conclusion

Japan's experience of limited sovereignty has taken distinct forms in two pivotal historical periods: the externally imposed legal constraints of the unequal treaties in the nineteenth century and the internally accepted limitations of the post-war Japan–U.S. security alliance. Both episodes profoundly shaped Japan's political autonomy and international positioning, albeit in divergent ways.

The era of unequal treaties, marked by extraterritoriality and loss of tariff autonomy, served as a catalyst for Japan's modernisation. These externally imposed constraints, while initially degrading, spurred a powerful drive toward national self-assertion, as scholars such as Pyle have argued. The imperative to reclaim full sovereignty galvanised industrial, legal, and military reforms, enabling Japan to emerge as a modern power capable of renegotiating its place in the international order.

By contrast, the post-war period involved a self-chosen limitation through the U.S. alliance framework, particularly the Security Treaty and Status of Forces Agreement (SOFA). While these arrangements ensured national security and facilitated economic recovery, they simultaneously circumscribed Japan's defence and foreign policy autonomy. This strategic dependence, though voluntary, has given rise to enduring tensions—particularly in constitutional debates over Article 9 and the future of the alliance—highlighting the complex interplay between sovereignty, security, and democratic accountability.

Taken together, these cases reveal that sovereignty is not a static or absolute concept, but a historically contingent and politically negotiated condition. Japan's trajectory illustrates how externally imposed constraints can trigger efforts toward autonomy, while internally accepted limitations may produce both stability and long-term dependency. The legacies of these two eras continue to shape contemporary debates on Japan's role in global affairs, including its responses to shifting geopolitical dynamics in the Asia-Pacific.

Ultimately, this study underscores that sovereignty in Japan has been both constrained and redefined through legal structures, strategic choices, and historical circumstances. By comparing these two periods, it becomes evident that Japan's political development has been forged not in the absence of sovereignty, but in the ongoing struggle to reclaim, redefine, and strategically manage it in an interdependent world.

References

- Aketagawa T (1999) *The Political History of the Japan-US Administrative Agreement: An Introduction to the Study of the Japan-US Status of Forces Agreement*. Tokyo: Hosei University Press.
- Aketagawa T (2017) *The Japan-U.S. Status of Forces Agreement: Its history and present*. Tokyo: Misuzu Shobo.
- Britannica (n.d.) *Sovereignty*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/sovereignty>
- Calder KE (1988) Japanese foreign economic policy formation: Explaining the reactive state. *World Politics* 40(4): 517–541. Doi:10.2307/2010317.
- Courts of Japan (n.d.) *Sunagawa case, judgment of the Supreme Court of Japan*. Available at: https://www.courts.go.jp/app/hanrei_jp/detail2?id=55816

- Fujiu, S (2024) Main issues and current situation regarding the implementation of the Japan-U.S. Status of Forces Agreement. Available at: https://www.sangiin.go.jp/japanese/annai/chousa/rippou_chousa/backnumber/20240920
- Green MJ (2010) Redefining and reaffirming the US-Japan alliance. *Asia Policy* 10(1): 16–20.
- Green, MJ and PM Cronin (1999) *The US-Japan Alliance: Past, Present, and Future*. Washington: Council on Foreign Relations Press.
- Guinto J (2024) US soldier charged in Japan for rape of minor. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/cpwwdyye4vgo>
- Hornung JW (2019) *Managing the U.S.-Japan Alliance: An Examination of Structural Linkages in the Security Relationship (Second Edition)*. Washington, D.C.: Sasakawa USA.
- Ikenberry GJ and Watanabe Y (2024) A New Trump presidency: The implications for US-Japan relations. Online seminar, accessible remotely via Zoom organised by the Daiwa Anglo-Japanese Foundation on 19 November. Available at: <https://dajf.org.uk/event/a-new-trump-presidency-the-implications-for-us-japan-relations>
- Inoguchi T (1998) Looking back to look forward: The Westphalian, Philadelphian, and Anti-Utopian paradigms. *International Studies Association March 1998*. Columbia University. Available at: <https://ciaotest.cc.columbia.edu/conf/into1/>
- Irie A (1966) *Japanese Diplomacy: From the Meiji Restoration to the Present*. Tokyo: CHUOKORON-SHINSHA. INC.
- Japan Center for Asian Historical Records (2018) *The Iwakura Mission: Tracking 150 people who crossed the oceans*. Available at: https://www.jacar.go.jp/english/iwakura_en/index.html
- Johnstone CB and J Schoff (2024) A vital next step for the U.S.-Japan Alliance: Command and control modernization. Center for Strategic & International Studies (CSIS). Available at: <https://www.csis.org/analysis/vital-next-step-us-japan-alliance-command-and-control-modernization>
- Kosaka M (1968/2006) *Prime Minister Shigeru Yoshida*. Tokyo: CHUOKORON-SHINSHA. INC.
- Krasner SD (1999) *Sovereignty: Organized Hypocrisy*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Krasner SD (2001) *Sovereignty*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3183223>
- Krasner SD (2004) Sharing sovereignty: New institutions for collapsed and failing states. *International Security* 29(2): 85–120.
- Lind J (2022) Japan Steps Up: How Asia's Rising Threats Convinced Tokyo to Abandon Its Defense Taboos. *Foreign Affairs*. Available at: https://www.foreignaffairs.com/japan/japan-steps?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Loughlin M (2017) The erosion of sovereignty. *Netherlands Journal of Legal Philosophy* 2: 57–81. Doi: 10.5553/NJLP/.000048.
- Mälksoo L (2017) Sources of international law in the 19th century. In: d'Aspremont J and Besson S (eds), *The Oxford Handbook on the Sources of International Law*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 1–21.
- Mears, H (translated by Nobuji Ito) (1948/2015) *Mirror for Americans: Japan*. [in Japanese] Tokyo: Kadokawa. (The original book: published in 1948 by Boston: Houghton, Mifflin).
- Ministry of Defense of Japan (2025) List of designated USFJ facilities and areas. Available at: <https://www.mod.go.jp/en/presiding/law/usfj.html>
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan (2024a) Japan-United States status of forces agreement and related information. Available at: <https://www.mofa.go.jp/mofaj/area/usa/sfa/kyoutei/index.html>
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan (2024b) *Diplomatic bluebook 2024*. Available at: https://www.mofa.go.jp/policy/other/bluebook/2024/pdf/en_index.html
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan (2025) *Japan-United States security arrangements*. Available at: <https://www.mofa.go.jp/region/n-america/us/security/index.html> (accessed 25 January 2025).

- Nakanishi H (2010) Diplomatic strategy of a defeated nation: Shigeru Yoshida's diplomacy and his successors. In: Ishizu T (ed) History of Strategic thought in Japan and the United States. Tokyo: Sairyusha, pp. 157–160.
- Nagao R (1979) Man and society in Nishi Amane. Annual Report of Legal Studies 1978.
- Nagao R (n.d.) Blog. Available at: http://ouranos2.web.fc2.com/1C_2FOLDER.html
- Nishi T (2005) MacArthur surrenders nation. Tokyo: CHUOKORON-SHINSHA, INC.
- Odaka A (1984) Introduction to Jurisprudence. Tokyo: Yuhikaku.
- Office of The Historian (U.S.) (1853) Milestones: 1830–1860: The United States and the opening to Japan, 1853. Available at: <https://history.state.gov/milestones/1830-1860/opening-to-japan#:~:text=The%20Japanese%20grudgingly%20agreed%20to,American%20ships%3A%20Shimoda%20and%20Hakodate>
- Office of the Historian (U.S.) (1952) No. 480 memorandum by the Secretary of State and the Secretary of Defence (Lovett) to the President: Arrangements for United States forces in Japan in the post-peace treaty period. Available at: <https://history.state.gov/historicaldocuments/frus1952-54v14p2/d480>
- Office of The Historian (U.S.) (1957a) 137. memorandum from the assistant secretary of state for far eastern affairs (Robertson) to the secretary of state. Available at: <https://history.state.gov/historicaldocuments/frus1955-57v23p1/d137>
- Office of The Historian (U.S.) (1957b) 158. Draft memorandum for the president prepared in the Department of State: The Girard case. Available at: <https://history.state.gov/historicaldocuments/frus1955-57v23p1/d158>
- Oros A (n.d.) The revision of the US-Japan security treaty in 1960: Lessons for the current standards alliance. National Institute for Defense Studies (NIDS) Data. Available at: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.nids.mod.go.jp/event/report/pdf/Anp050th_s_07.pdf
- Pyle KB (1996) The Making of Modern Japan. Belmont: Wadsworth Pub Co.
- Ryukyu Shimposha (2004). The concept of the Japan-US status of forces agreement: Confidential documents of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs: Revised Edition. Tokyo: Koubunken.
- Sakurada D (1997) WP No. 07/97: For mutual benefit: the Japan-US security treaty: From a Japanese perspective. Centre for Strategic Studies, Victoria University of Wellington. Available at: <https://www.wgtn.ac.nz/strategic-studies/publications-and-research/publications-archive/working-papers>
- Sakurai Y (2023) International cooperation of Asian law systems beyond diversity. Political Reflection Magazine 9(3): 27–31.
- Shahabuddin M (2019) The 'standard of civilisation' in international law: Intellectual perspectives from pre-war Japan. Leiden Journal of International Law 32(1): 13–32. DOI: 10.1017/S0922156518000559.
- Tagami J (1962) The concept of sovereignty. Hitotsubashi University Research Annual Report, Law Studies 4: 1–22.
- Tanaka A (n.d.) "The World and Japan" database: Security treaty between Japan and the United States of America. Available at: <https://worldjpn.net/documents/texts/docs/19510908.T2E.html>
- Terashima J and Kurashige A (2024) Terashima Jiro's "Japan revitalisation initiative" - a paradigm shift in the Japan-US alliance. The Economist Online. Available: <https://weekly-economist.mainichi.jp/articles/20240606/se1/00m/020/002000d>
- The Asahi Shimbun (2024a) Editorial: Top court chief's behaviour during Sunagawa case crossed the line. Available at: <https://www.asahi.com/ajw/articles/15125438>
- The Asahi Shimbun (2024b) Editorial: Forceful way Futenma base is being relocated a national disgrace. Available at: <https://www.asahi.com/ajw/articles/15569358>
- The Diet, House of Representatives, the Committee of Foreign Affairs (2022), Diet proceedings (Katsuya Okada vs. Yohimasa Hayashi). Available at: <https://kokkai.ndl.go.jp/#/>

- The Mainichi (2019) Editorial: Change pact with US forces to give Japan full control of Tokyo air traffic. Available at: <https://mainichi.jp/english/articles/20190218/p2a/oom/ona/011000c>
- Yabe K (2017). *You must not know: The Hidden Structure of Japanese Domination*. Tokyo: Kodansha Ltd.
- Yoshida T (2016) *Research on the Japan-U.S. Security Consultative Committee: Uncovering the mysterious power structure (Postwar Rediscovery series; 5)*. Tokyo: SOGENSHA Inc.

Journal of Politics and Development

ISSN 2632-4911

Volume 15 ■ Number 2 ■ Summer 2025